

Annex 1. Potential pathways for pathogen transmission and spread in a defined WLI and the relevance of wildlife

Once the main characteristics of the target epidemiological units are known, the following checklist may help to consider possible risks and transmission pathways (in both directions). This checklist is adaptable to any WLI and therefore, it provides a flexible framework to develop WLI-specific On-farm Wildlife Risk Mitigation Protocols. We provide an open list which needs to be adapted considering the specificities of the target WLI.

Potential pathways and risks for pathogen transmission and spread in a defined WLI	Relevance of wildlife (darker=higher risk)
<p>Farmed animal species and management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Species (or mixed species); presence of other farmed species in, or in contact with, the epidemiological unit (e.g., shared pastures, scattered grazing plots) - Farming system (grazing-based, open-air, indoor) - Herd or flock size 	<p>Plot or pasture rotation and other activities can increase the risk of wildlife-livestock interactions. There is an obvious biosecurity gradient with the highest risk in grazing-based systems, which are most exposed to the WLI, intermediate risk in (fenced) open-air production and lowest risk in indoor production systems. However, a zero risk does not exist and there are risk mitigation measures available for all kinds of systems. A larger number of farmed animals increases the chances transmission at the WLI.</p>
<p>Location and distance to other epidemiological units:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surface - Density of epidemiological units, distances - Periurban or rural 	<p>Location, size, extension, and distance to other establishments imply risks. For instance, dense farming areas might represent a good habitat for synanthropic wildlife. Larger farms will be more difficult to protect from wildlife by perimeter fencing.</p>
<p>(Domestic) animal movements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of new animals - Transhumance and transterminance - Moving livestock to grazing grounds or water points - Movement of animals through vertically integrated production systems 	<p>Relevant if wildlife is present at farm, area of origin or area of destiny (WLI).</p> <p>Potential role of other farmed species as bridge hosts after interactions with wildlife.</p>
<p>Building and fencing characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permanent farm buildings for animals or for storage - Perimeter fencing of the epidemiological unit (and door characteristics) - Public roads or paths crossing the farm 	<p>If buildings are used for confining domestic animals permanently or seasonally (e.g., in winter), or if buildings are used for feed storage, it is convenient to assess if these are accessible to wild mammals, peridomestic birds, and vectors. The presence of perimeter fencing is a key biosecurity measure. Are</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interior fencing for plot/use division 	<p>these physical barriers around key facilities/buildings against target wildlife?</p>
<p>Habitats and land uses (in and around):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fruit trees or mast trees - Trees attracting birds - Crops in the epidemiological unit - Nearby crops - Nearby wetlands - Nearby woodlands - Nearby protected areas - Hunting areas 	<p>The habitat drives the composition and abundance of wildlife. Trees in the epidemiological unit might attract wild birds for nesting or roosting. These may act as bridge hosts. Nearby wetlands (even outside the epidemiological unit) drive wild bird presence and abundance. Nearby woodlands or protected areas may imply higher wildlife densities. If the epidemiological unit is in or close to a hunting zone, baiting and carcass dressing may suppose a risk. Habitat characteristics and wildlife use vary seasonally.</p>
<p>Rodents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Synanthropic rodents such as rats and mice living in the buildings - Rodents present in the epidemiological unit 	<p>May play a role as maintenance hosts or bridge hosts.</p>
<p>Interaction with wildlife:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant wildlife species (see appendix #) - Behavior of wildlife and livestock - Direct, on pasture or at feeding or watering points - Indirect, often feed- or water-mediated 	<p>Most relevant transmission pathway at the WLI, particularly in pasture-based and open-air systems and through indirect contacts. Flying wildlife and rodents may more easily access the interior of farm buildings. Some WLIs are restricted to a single livestock and wildlife species (e.g., classical swine fever) while others are multi-host infections (e.g., influenza). Some risk species have an almost global distribution. Others have a restricted geographical range. Wildlife presence/abundance can be assessed through signs of presence, camera traps, hunting bag, or frequency of sighting by farmers (see Box #).</p>
<p>Aerosols:</p>	<p>Requires relatively close direct contact allowing aerosol transmission. Examples include foot and mouth disease, Aujeszky's disease and respiratory diseases such as avian influenza → check if wild birds access inside buildings.</p>
<p>Arthropods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biological vectors - Mechanical vectors 	<p>A complete vector-proofing is challenging, even in modern farm buildings. Consider micro-habitats for vectors in and around the epidemiological unit.</p>
<p>Vehicles entering and traversing the property:</p>	<p>Relevant if wildlife is present at farm, area of origin (WLI) of vehicles.</p>

<p>People:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Staff - External services - Visitors - Hunters 	<p>Relevant if people interact with wildlife (e.g., hunters). Consumption of wildlife products inside the farm.</p>
<p>Equipment and fomites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transport means - Machinery - Boots and clothing - (...) 	<p>Relevant for pathogens that the staff of the farm may indirectly spread during routine activities, often from the immediate surroundings of the farm where wildlife may access.</p>
<p>Feed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pastures - Concentrate storage and feeding - Volume feed storage and feeding - Swill feeding - (...) 	<p>Feed is attractive to both wildlife and livestock, and hence its distribution does influence the direct and indirect contact risks at the WLI. This includes especially sites with concentrates such as grain or composed feed but also sites rich in natural forage and sites with volume feed such as hay. Forage harvested in infected wildlife areas can be contaminated. Flying wildlife and rodents may access indoor storages. Stored animal feed can also become contaminated if accessible to wildlife. Feeding practices (e.g., concentrate feeding in winter) can also attract wildlife promoting contact and transmission.</p>
<p>Bedding and enrichment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harvest and storage - Used bedding management 	<p>Materials harvested in infected wildlife habitats can be contaminated.</p>
<p>Water:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Watering - Waterways - Drainage 	<p>Water is a key means of indirect infection transmission and attracts both wildlife and livestock, especially in arid climates, enabling intra- and cross-species contacts at aggregation points. Therefore, water availability and distribution and the characteristics of waterpoints such as streams and rivers, ponds and waterholes, or troughs and other watering devices are of special relevance in risk assessment at the WLI. Wildlife and livestock may contaminate water through excretions/secretions. Water upstream may become contaminated by wildlife or domestic animals.</p>
<p>Waste:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slurry/manure - Carcasses 	<p>Farm waste management is not only relevant to reduce the risks of infection spread, but also to avoid attracting wildlife to the farm premises. European badgers and wild boar, as well as many peridomestic wild birds, are attracted by livestock waste (including slurry ponds) in search of earthworms and other invertebrates. Wildlife may also access slurry/manure when used as fertilizer. This</p>

	<p>implies a risk of pathogen transmission from farmed animals to wildlife but also a risk to farmed animals due to increased wildlife presence. Infected/contaminated livestock carcasses might attract wildlife. Wildlife remains, e.g., from hunting activities in or around the epidemiological unit represent a risk for livestock. Access of scavengers and wildlife in general, to carcasses - carcass storage system (e.g., containers) and carcass destruction system.</p>
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